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Abstract

This paper discusses the various uses, advantages, and needs of pressure sensors in agriculture. The primary objective of this research is to develop a mathematical model for the PZT-5J based piezoelectric pressure sensor used in bridge structures for sensing 10kPa to 100 kPa applied pressure. These pressure sensor ranges are used to measure the pressure of air, water, and oil. To identify the variables influencing the sensor's output, mechanical and electrostatic mathematical modeling techniques are used. The outcome of the mathematical analyses is validated through simulation using the COMSOL 5.2 multiphysics simulator for 3D structural analysis. The estimated mathematical stresses of the sensor and the simulated mechanical stress output are compared. Analyses are also conducted on the simulated output voltage and the voltage computed mathematically. The factors affecting the sensor's output voltage include its length, thickness of the bridge, thickness of the piezoelectric, Young's modulus and the piezoelectric voltage coefficient (g_{31}). The output voltage is negative in value because the stress produced by the applied pressure on the piezoelectric material is tensile stress.

Keywords: charge coefficient, negative slope, moment of inertia, stress, voltage coefficient.

Introduction

The need for agriculture to generate more food grows as the world's population expands. The use of pressure sensors is one of the most important technological breakthroughs in agriculture today. A pressure sensor is a tool that gauges a fluid or gas's pressure. Pressure sensors are used in agriculture to monitor and control the pressure of water and other fluids. There is various application of pressure sensor in the various filed. Machinery: Modern agricultural sprayers use pressure sensors that measure the spray bar's pressure, allowing for exact fertilizer and chemical delivery. This is significant because the precise amount of water and nutrients that crops receive determines their growth and production. Farmers can make sure that their crops are receiving the ideal amount of water and nutrients by employing pressure sensors. Weather Monitoring: For pressure monitoring and weather forecasting, the device's built-in high-precision features are crucial. These features include a high-precision air pressure sensor with high stability, little drift, high sensitivity, and high repeatability. Soil Health Monitoring: Farmers can assess if the soil is compacted or has enough moisture by monitoring the pressure in the soil. The use of fertilizer and other soil management techniques can be modified using this knowledge. Farmers can guarantee the health and productivity of their crops by keeping healthy soil. Watering livestock: To monitor the water pressure in the systems, pressure sensors are used. This guarantees that the animals have access to clean, fresh water at all times [1-4].

There are various pressure sensors based on their sensing properties. They are resistive, capacitive, inductive, optical and piezoelectric [5-9]. The capacity of some dielectric materials to produce electric charges when mechanically or physically deformed is known as piezoelectricity. Since this phenomenon is linked to spontaneous polarization caused by the displacement of electrons from the atomic centre, piezoelectric materials are used for sensing the continuously changing physical quantities. The most promising pressure sensor for IoT is piezoelectric pressure sensor as they are highly sensitive and consumed less power. The advantages of piezoelectric pressure sensors include frequency response, a negligibly small amount of phase shift, low cost, small size and integration into MEMS, no external power requirement, and great adaptability and ability to be created in any shape or size.

Scope of the Work

MEMS pressure sensors are frequently used to monitor and control low and high pressure in a variety of applications. The design principle and analysis of such a MEMS pressure sensor still presents

a difficulty, though, as MEMS technology necessitates a full understanding of multiple disciplines, including mechanical, electronic, and physics, among others.

Fig. 1: The work flow of this study.

A mathematical model and simulation of the design sensor are required before prototyping in order to save time, money, and improve device performance. The mathematical model for the sensor is being created, but there is a significant research deficit. The mathematical model is validated by the simulated values. Further a conclusion is made for this study.

Quantification of CH₄ using neural network.

For this work, a three-dimensional model of a bridge beam-based piezoelectric pressure sensor is proposed, with Silicon (Si) serving as the sensor main structure, Silicon-dioxide (SiO₂) serving as the insulator, PZT-5J as the piezoelectric material and Gold (Au) serving as the electrode as shown in Fig. 2 and the dimension of the model sensor is tabulated in table 1.

Fig. 2: 3D Model of proposed piezoelectric pressure.**Table 1: Dimensions of the proposed piezoelectric pressure sensor.**

Material	Dimension		
	Length	Breadth	Thickness/Height
Substrate	300 μm	75 μm	75 μm
Insulator	300 μm	75 μm	3 μm
Electrode	75 μm	75 μm	5 μm
Piezoelectric	75 μm	75 μm	10 μm

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Mathematical Modeling of the Sensor

The mathematical model is divided in two portion i.e., mechanical model and electrostatic model.

Mechanical model: It is necessary to evaluate the stress on the bridge structure as the output voltage of the piezoelectric is directly proportional to the induced stress. Consider the displacement function of the bridge structure as follows to get the stress [10-11]:

$$-EI \frac{\partial^2 w(x)}{\partial x^2} = \frac{Fx}{2} - \frac{Fx^2}{2l} - m_0 \quad (1)$$

Where: E represents the Young's modulus, I represents the moment of inertia, x represents the point on the beam, $w(x)$ is deflection of a beam at the position x , F represents the applied force on the sensor, l represents the length of the bridge, and m_0 is the moment at the clamped.

By definition of uniformly applied force, we can express

$$F = PA \quad (2)$$

$$A = lb \quad (3)$$

Where, P represents the pressure, A represents the area, b represents the breadth of the beam.

While integrated Eq.1 with respect to x and applying the condition that the derivative of the deflection at $x = l$ is Zero. We get the value of

$$m_0 = \frac{Fl}{12} \quad (4)$$

The value of moment of inertia I is given by

$$I = \frac{bh^3}{12} \quad (5)$$

where, h is the thickness of the beam.

In [11], the equation of the stress on the bridge is given by:

$$T(x) = -Ez \frac{\partial^2 w(x)}{\partial x^2} \quad (6)$$

Where, z represents the distance between point x and the beam's natural plane. Eq. 1 can be written in the following way:

$$\frac{\partial^2 w(x)}{\partial x^2} = -\left(\frac{Fx}{2} - \frac{Fx^2}{2l} - m_0\right) \frac{1}{EI} \quad (7)$$

Now, substituting the values of m_0 and I in the above Eq. 7. We get

$$\frac{\partial^2 w(x)}{\partial x^2} = -\left(\frac{Fx}{2} - \frac{Fx^2}{2l} - m_0\right) \frac{12}{Ebh^3} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 w(x)}{\partial x^2} = -(6xl - 6x^2 - l^2) \frac{F}{Elbh^3} \quad (9)$$

Substituting the value $\frac{\partial^2 w(x)}{\partial x^2}$, Eq. 6 can be written as

$$T(x) = \frac{zF(6x^2 - 6xl + l^2)}{lbh^3}$$

$$T(x) = \frac{zPA(6x^2 - 6xl + l^2)}{lbh^3}$$

$$T(x) = \frac{zPbl(6x^2 - 6xl + l^2)}{lbh^3}$$

$$T(x) = \frac{zP(6x^2 - 6xl + l^2)}{h^3} \quad (10)$$

Let's examine at the derivatives of the above equation in terms of x .

$$\frac{dT(x)}{dx} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{zP(6x^2 - 6xl + l^2)}{h^3} \right)$$

$$\frac{dT(x)}{dx} = \left(\frac{zP(12x - 6l)}{h^3} \right) \quad (11)$$

For finding the minimum stress the above Eq. 11 is equating to zero and find the value of position x , $0 \leq x \leq l$.

$$0 = \left(\frac{zP(12x - 6l)}{h^3} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$zP(12x - 6l) = 0$$

$$x = \frac{l}{2}$$

We needed to figure out the maximum stress values because the smallest stress occurs in the middle of the bridge structure. The minimum value of stress will be

$$T_{\min} \left(\frac{l}{2} \right) = -\frac{zPl^2}{2h^3} \quad (13)$$

Now for maximum stress the $(6x^2 - 6xl + l^2)$ much be maximum for $0 \leq x \leq l$, so the maximum value will be stress occurs at $x = l$ or 0 on

the upper surface. So the maximum stress will be $\frac{zPl^2}{h^3}$.

$$T_{\max}(l) = T_{\max}(0) = \frac{zPl^2}{h^3}. \quad (14)$$

From the above Eq. 14, the maximum stress is depends on the length of the bridge, thickness of the bridge, distance from the natural plane and applied pressure.

Electrostatic Modeling: The voltage of the circuit can be calculated as given in Eq. 15.

$$V = Q / C \quad (15)$$

Where, V represents the voltage, Q represents the charges and C represents the capacitance between the two piezoelectric surface.

The structure of the bridge is used in a transverse mode. The following Eq. 15 describes the electrostatic charges produced by generated stress on the piezoelectric layer in the transverse mode of operation:

$$q(x) = T(x, y)d_{31}, \quad (16)$$

Where $q(x)$ is the charge produced on the surface at location x or charge density and d_{31} is the piezoelectric material's strain constant. Stress in a bridge construction is just a function of x , hence $T(x, y)$ can be swapped out for $T(x)$. Now

$$q(x) = T(x)d_{31}, \quad (17)$$

The surface's overall charge development is given by

$$Q(x) = bl_{pizo}q(x), \quad (18)$$

$$Q(x) = bl_{pizo}T(x)d_{31}, \quad (19)$$

Where $Q(x)$ is the total charge that formed on the piezoelectric surface, l_{pizo} is the piezoelectric length.

Consequently, the capacitance that formed between the two surfaces is given by $C = \frac{bl_{pizo}T(x)d_{31}}{V(x)}$,

$$(20)$$

$$\frac{\epsilon_{33}A_{pizo}}{t} = \frac{bl_{pizo}T(x)d_{31}}{V(x)}, \quad (21)$$

Where, ϵ_{33} represents the dielectric constant of the piezoelectric material. Since the A_{pizo} is the surface area of the piezoelectric, t is the piezoelectric thickness and $V(x)$ is the piezoelectric output voltage.

$$\epsilon_{33} = \frac{d_{31}}{g_{31}}. \quad (22)$$

Where, g_{31} is the piezoelectric voltage coefficient in shear mode.

Now, substituting the value of d_{31} in Eq. 22, the piezoelectric output voltage is

$$V(x) = T(x)t \frac{d_{31}}{\epsilon_{33}}, \quad (23)$$

$$V(x) = T(x)tg_{31}, \quad (24)$$

The output voltage of the piezoelectric pressure sensor depends on the stress induced on the piezoelectric material, thickness of the piezoelectric material and the piezoelectric voltage coefficient.

1. Simulation Output and Discussion

The COMSOL Multiphysics simulator based on the finite element technique (FEM) is used in simulation for various assessments of the 3D model of the sensor with the dimension as tabulated in table

1. The Young's modulus of the Au, SiO₂ and Si are 70 GPa, 70 GPa and 160 GPa respectively. The Young's modulus, Piezoelectric charge constant and piezoelectric voltage coefficient of PZT-5J are 51×10^9 Pa, -270×10^{-12} C/N and -10.4×10^{-3} Vm/N.

Fig. 3: Stress distribution on PZT-5J based sensor.

The simulation is run with a step size of 5 kPa with input pressures ranging from 10 kPa to 100 kPa. The output stress for the simulation is shown in fig. 3. Here we see the maximum output stress is occurred at the clamp area of the bridge and minimum stress occurred at the middle of the bridge.

Table 2: The calculated and simulated stress outputs of the different piezoelectric material.

Pressure (kPa)	PZT-5J(Pa)		Pressure (kPa)	PZT-5J(Pa)	
	Sim	Cal		Sim	Cal
10	50194	52915	60	306610	317490
15	75736	79372	65	338290	343940
20	100510	105830	70	354160	370400
25	130110	132290	75	383270	396860
30	156140	158740	80	420260	423320
35	173260	185200	85	446520	449770
40	202110	211660	90	464110	476230
45	226540	238120	95	501120	502690
50	251270	264570	100	520450	529150
55	281060	291030	-	-	-

The graphical representation of the table 2 is shown in fig. 5. From this graph the output stress of the simulated and calculated are very closed to each other and they are linearly vary with the applied pressure. So the mathematical model that is developed can be implemented for future application.

The simulated and calculated values of the output voltage of the sensor are tabulated in table 3. The output voltage of the sensor is showing in the range of mV which is very high voltage for such a micro level sensor.

Table 3: Calculated vs Simulated output voltages of PZT-5J based piezoelectric pressure sensor.

Pressure (kPa)	PZT-5J(V)		Pressure (kPa)	PZT-5J(V)	
	Sim	Cal		Sim	Cal
10	-0.00335	-0.0050	60	-0.02013	-0.0300
15	-0.00503	-0.0075	65	-0.02181	-0.0325
20	-0.00671	-0.0100	70	-0.02349	-0.0350

Fig. 4 displays the sensor's simulated output voltages for a number of piezoelectric sensors. Despite the fact that the output voltages are directly proportional in magnitude, these values have a negative slope. This output values are negative because the stress induced at the surface is tensile stress.

Fig. 4: Simulated Output on PZT-5J based sensor.

The simulated and calculated values of stress are tabulated in table 2 for the comparative study. The stress induced on the surface of piezoelectric materials increase as the applied pressure increase.

Fig. 5: The simulated and calculated values of stress for the applied pressure.

The output values are showing negative values as the induced stress is tensile stress. For the calculated values the g_{31} is a negative value. The output values and simulated values are also very closed to each other so, the mathematical model of the output voltage is validated.

25	-0.00849	-0.0125	75	-0.02517	-0.0375
30	-0.01007	-0.0150	80	-0.02684	-0.0400
35	-0.01174	-0.0175	85	-0.02852	-0.0425
40	-0.01342	-0.0200	90	-0.03020	-0.0451
45	-0.01510	-0.0225	95	-0.03188	-0.0476
50	-0.01678	-0.0250	100	-0.03350	-0.0501
55	-0.01845	-0.0275	-	-	-

The graphical representation of the output voltage for calculated and simulated is shown in fig. 6. From this figure the output voltage is increase in magnitude with increase in applied voltage but the slope is negative. This characteristic is predicted in the mathematical model.

Fig. 6: The simulated and calculated values of output voltage for the applied pressure.

The various factors affecting the output voltage of the sensors are piezoelectric voltage coefficient, thickness of the piezoelectric, length of the bridge, thickness of the bridge, distance from the natural plane and applied pressure.

Conclusion

Piezoelectric pressure based on bridge beams is designed and modeled. The different applications benefits and requirements of pressure sensors in agriculture are discussed in this study. Mechanical modeling and electrostatic modeling are the two phases in the development of the mathematical model of the sensor.

A 3D model of a sensor is created for simulation in the COMSOL multiphysics simulator. Following several observations was discovered that the calculated and simulated stress outputs were reasonably close to one another so the mathematical model is validated. As a result, the mathematical model and design flow may be used to determine the stress and voltage generated on the piezoelectric sensor's surface using bridges structure. Surfaces under tensile strain develop a negative voltage, whereas surfaces under compressive stress produce a positive voltage. Stress, Young's modulus, thickness of the bridge and the piezoelectric, position of the piezoelectric, piezoelectric voltage coefficient, and operating mode of the piezoelectric layer are all factors that affect the sensor's output voltage. In response to the applied pressure, the voltage output varies linearly in magnitude with a downward slope. The slope is downward because the induce voltage is due to the tensile stress produced on the piezoelectric surface by the applied stress. A pressure sensor that is

suitable for the application can be designed using the mathematical model that has been constructed.

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